

Research Article

<p>A WORD AND ITS RELATIVES: DERIVATION IN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE</p>		<p style="text-align: center;">Morphology</p> <p>Keywords: word, word-formation, derivation, lexemes, conversion, etc.</p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">Abstract</p> <p>This study makes an effort to contrast word derivation in English and Albanian. English is a versatile and highly productive language. Because it is universal, it may incorporate new words and go through a variety of word formation processes to expand its lexicon. Derivation is one of several procedures for word development. The fundamental processes by which words are formed in the English and Albanian languages are quite similar. There are conversions for prefix, suffix, and affixes in the English language. Prefix, suffix, prefix-suffix, and non-affix derivations are all present in the Albanian language.</p>		

1. Introduction

Morphology is the study of the internal structure of words. Its etymology is Greek: *morph*-meaning ‘*shape, form*’, this means that *morphology* is the study of *form* or *forms*. In biology morphology refers to the study of the form and structure of organisms, and in geology it refers to the study of the configuration and evolution of land forms. In linguistics morphology refers to the mental system involved in word formation or to the branch of linguistics that deals with words, their internal structure, and how they are formed.

English is considered a very productive language because of its universal nature. It can endure many different word formation processes to create new lexicon. Some of these processes are more lexicalized, such as derivation or compounding. Derivation is the process of creating separate but morphologically related words. But there are also some minor methods of word-formation e.g.: clipping, blending and conversion, which have not been much studied yet. Linguists have different opinions about the way they should be treated. But there is only one point they all agree with. They consider that these new methods are becoming more frequently used. They suppose that conversion will be more active in the future, and so, it will create a great part of the new words appearing in the English language. Lexemes take a part in this paper. The different shapes of lexemes in English language were discussed. Also word classes and their classification are treated in this paper.

In Albanian, derivation is the most productive and diversified method in the system of word formation. There are four kinds of derivations: prefix derivations, suffix derivations, prefix-suffix derivations and non-affix derivations. Lexemes and their classification because they are very important for word-formation in Albanian language.

Also conversion, compounding, blending, etc. are methods of word-formation in Albanian language. Conversion which is a very productive way of forming a new word by changing its grammatical class. By changing the grammatical class, the word formed this way changes the paradigm also.

2. A word and its relatives: derivation

Word is a part of every one's vocabulary and that's why we all think we understand what words are. The field of morphology studies and analyses the form of words by factorizing them into morphemes which are the smallest meaningful units the word can be divided in. Even a letter can be the smallest unit of word, but even though the morpheme is considered a meaningful unit it does not mean that every morpheme can be a word. Words and morphemes are linguistic signs. The formation of a word from another word or from a root in the same or another language is called derivation.¹ Most of the time, but not always, it involves one or more changes in form. It can involve prefixing and suffixing. English allows us to change a word's part of speech without any change of form. As a result of this change, identical forms may belong to different parts of speech. Derivation involves the creation of one lexeme from another, such as *selector* or *selection* from *select*. Derivation generally results in a change in lexical meaning or the lexical category of a particular word.²

The basic ways of forming words in word-derivation in English language are:

1. Prefixation, which is the process of deriving a new word by attaching a prefix to the front of a root or base? For example, *unhappy*, *decode*, *improper*, *illegal*, *mislead*, etc. Some prefixes are productive, others less so.³ Many new words are formed by adding a prefix to the beginning of a Latin or Greek root or word. E.g. *ambiguous*, *multiple*, *dictation* (Latin), *autonomy*, *biology*, *homonym* (Greek).
2. Suffixation, which is the process of deriving a new word by attaching a suffix at the end of the root or base. For example, *comfortable*, *flavorless*, *happily*, *terrible*, *grateful*, etc. Some suffixes are productive, others are less so. Some suffixes are native. Others come from Latin, often through French or Greek.⁴ Many words are formed by adding a suffix to the Latin or Greek root. E.g. *percent*, *conform*, *transmit* (Latin), *telegram*, *psychology*, *antonym* (Greek).
3. Affixation, which is the formation of a new word with the help of affixes: *pointless* (from *point*). Affixes may be derivational, like English *-ness* and *pre-*, or inflectional, like English plural *-s* and past tense *-ed*. Affixation is, thus, the linguistic process speakers use to form different words by adding affixes at the beginning which is called Prefixation and at the end which is called the suffixation of words.

¹ <http://www.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/derivation>

² Aronoff, M. and Fudeman, K., "What is Morphology?", Willey Blackwell, 2011, p. 47, 48

³ Hamawand, Z. "Morphology in English: Word Formation in Cognitive Grammar", London 2011, p. 55

⁴ Hamawand, Z. "Morphology in English: Word Formation in Cognitive Grammar", London 2011, p. 121

4. Conversion, which is the formation of a new word by bringing a stem of this word into a different formal model: *a fall (from to fall), a cut (from to cut)*.

Albanian language is also very rich with derived words. The method of derivation is the most productive in the system of word formation. Derivation is the forming of new words by joining word-formation affixes with lexemes or other words. According to the type of affix, there are four kinds of derivations in Albanian language:

1. Prefix derivations: which are also present in English. They are formed by adding a prefix to the word or lexeme, e.g.: *mosbesim, stergjysh, mbicmoj, carmatos*, etc. Prefixes in general do not change the lexical-grammatical category of the word, but they give a new supplemental meaning. Prefixation in Albanian language is developed in a close relationship with perngjitje, e.g.: *paradite, paraluftes, pasdreke*, etc., and with composition, e.g.: *pasardhes, praparoje, prapaskene*, etc.
2. Suffix derivations: forming new words by adding by adding a suffix to lexemes, e.g., *letersi, harketar, luftoj, majtas*, etc. In Albanian language the number of suffixes is bigger than the number of prefixes. By adding suffixes to the lexemes we form nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs, etc. Suffixes in general have a classific function that means that together with the new meaning they that they give to the lexeme they also determine the word class the new word belongs to. For e.g.: (nouns) *nxenes, gazetar, gjahtar, drejtor*, (adjectives) *terheqes, legjendar, arsimor, mesdhetar*, etc.
3. Prefix-suffix derivations: the lexeme takes a prefix and a suffix at the same time and the both morphemes have the role of a single word forming. For e.g.: *perkrenare, perfundoj, pergenjeshtroj, ndergjyqes, shfrytezoj*, etc. This kind of derivation is less productive.
4. Non-affix derivations: there are some words that from the semantic perspective are derived, but from the structural perspective they appear without any word forming affix. For e.g.: *hap-i, mund-i, shkul-i*, etc. formed from the verbs *hap, mund, shkul*.⁵

2.1 Relationship between lexemes

A lexeme is a meaningful linguistic unit that is an item in the vocabulary of a language.⁶ Lexemes are abstract subjects and can be thought of as sets of word-forms. Lexeme names are given in bold italics. For example *crow*, is that as a transitive verb it would get one entry despite the existence of four different shapes in which it appears: *crow, crows, crowned, crowning*. These different shapes spell out word forms that belong to the verb lexeme *crow*. In a big and detailed dictionary they would all be listed in the single entry for *crow*. In shorter dictionaries you would just be expected to know that the word forms for a regular verb like *crow* would be *crow, crows, crowned, crowning*, the word forms for a regular verb like *walk* would be *walk, walks, walked, walking*, and so on: they list the lexemes, you are meant to know the grammar.

⁵ Jashari, A. and Kryeziu, B. "GjuheAmtare: (njohuri per gjuhen, fonetike, morfologji, sintakse)", Universiteti Prishtine, Prishtine, 2011, p. 143, 144, 145

⁶ Merriam-Webster's 11th Collegiate Dictionary

There would be another lexeme in the dictionary for *crown*, of course: a noun lexeme *crown*. Its word forms would be the plain singular *crown*, the plain plural *crowns*, the genitive singular *crown's*, and the genitive plural *crowns'*.

The most basic concept of morphology is 'word'. But when a dictionary is made, not every sequence of letter or sounds has its own entry. For instance, the *live*, *lives*, *lived*, *living* are pronounced and written and are different words. But a dictionary will list only a single entry *live*. Dictionary users are expected to know that *live*, *lives*, *lived*, and *living* are different realizations of the 'same' word *live*. Thus, there are two different notions of 'word': the dictionary word and text word.

Distinguishing the lexemes in Albanian language is considered very important for word-formation.

- a) A lexeme is the part of word that remains after we remove the endings and suffixes (if it has any), e.g. *det-i*, *shok-un*, *trim-ave*, *rro-fsha*, etc.
- b) A word-forming lexeme is a lexeme by which is formed a (jo e parme) lexeme, e.g. *besë-nik*, *besnik-ëri*, *besnikëri-sht*, etc.
- c) A morphological lexeme is the part of word that remains after we remove only the ending (not the suffix), e.g. *lisa-ve*, *lisa-t*, etc.⁷

2.2 Word classes and conversion

All words belong to categories called word classes (or parts of speech) according to the part they play in a sentence. Word classes are a set of words that display the same formal properties, especially their inflections and distribution. Similar to the more traditional term part of speech. The two major families of word classes are:

1. Lexical (or open) classes: nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs
2. Function (or closed) classes: determiners, particles, prepositions, and others.⁸

The lexical and grammatical meaning distinction determines the first separation in our classification: form-class words and structure-class words. The form classes generally provide the primary lexical content and the structure classes explain the grammatical or structural relationship. We can easily recognize the class of a word by its use in context. Some words have suffixes (endings added to words to form new words) that help to signal the class they belong to. This doesn't mean that suffixes are necessarily sufficient in themselves to identify the class of a word. For example, adverbs are formed by adding the *-ly* suffix to the adjective *quick-ly*, *bad-ly*, but we also find this suffix in adjectives: *coward-ly*, *home-ly* and *man-ly*. And we can sometimes convert words from one class to another even though they have suffixes that are typical of their original

⁷ Jashari, A. and Kryeziu, B. "GjuheAmtare: (njohuri per gjuhen, fonetike, morfologji, sintakse)", Universiteti i Prishtines, Prishtine, 2011, p.140,141

⁸ Nordquist, R. "Glossary of Grammatical and Rhetorical Terms"

class: *an engineer, to engineer; a negative response, a negative*. All words in Albanian language are distributed into word classes or lexical categories which are called parts of speech. The affiliation of a word into this or that part of speech is determined from the lexical meaning and grammatical features. Depending only in lexical or grammatical criteria in many cases it doesn't allow words to distinguish from one another as part of speech. Also relying only in grammatical criteria in many cases makes impossible the distinguishing between the words that belong to different parts of speech.⁹ Classifying words into parts of speech we rely into these criteria: a) lexical criteria, b) morphological criteria and c) syntactical criteria. Based on morphological features parts of speech are distinguished into open and closed classes. Open classes: noun, pronoun, adjective, verb and numeral. Closed classes: adverb, preposition, conjunction, particles and interjection.¹⁰

2.2.1 Conversion

Conversion is the process of forming a new word from an existing word merely by changing the grammatical class of the latter word. Conversion may or may not involve the change of stress patterns. The same word assumes different classes in conversion. For example, the noun *email* appeared in English before the verb: *a decade ago I would have sent you an email* (noun) whereas *now I can either send you an email* (noun) or *simply email* (verb) *you*.¹¹ The original noun *email* experienced conversion, thus resulting in the new verb *email*. Conversion is also referred to as zero derivation or null derivation with the assumption that the formal change between words results in the addition of an invisible morpheme. Some other cases of conversion are listed below:

a. Noun to verb

the bottle-to bottle

the hammer-to hammer

the file-to file

the skin-to skin

the water-to water

b. Verb to noun

to call-a call

to dump-a dump

to guess-a guess

to jump - a jump

to spy - a spy

⁹Dhrimo, A., Angoni, F., Hysa, E., Lafi, E., Likaj, E., Agalliu, Sh., Demiraj, Sh., "Gramatika e Gjuhes se SotmeLetrareShqipe (Morfologjia)", ETMM i KSAK, Prishtine, 1989, p.11

¹⁰Jashari, A. and Kryeziu, B. "GjuheAmtare: (njohuri per gjuhen, fonetike, morfologji, sintakse)", UniversitetiPrishtines, Prishtine, 2011, p.133,134

¹¹Adedimeji, M.A. and Alabi, T.A. "Basic Elements of Analyzing Language and Grammar"

c. Adjective to verb*better - to better**empty - to empty**hip - to hip**open - to open**rustproof-to rustproof***d. Adjective to noun***poor - the poor**rich - the rich**well-fed - the well-fed**blind - the blind**sublime- the sublime*¹²

Conversion is particularly common in English because the basic form of nouns and verbs is identical in many cases.

Linguists are not very sure about the status of conversion. It is a bit unclear. It surely must be placed in the word-formation group, but there are some doubts about whether it must be considered a branch of this undetermined derivation or a separate process by itself, with the same status as derivation or compounding. Apart from position in grammar, some linguists claim that conversion will become even more active in the future. They are convinced because it is a very easy way to create new words in English. It is impossible to know the number of conversions that appear every day in the spoken language, although we know this number must be high. And because it is a quite recent phenomenon, the written evidence is not a fully believable source. So the only way is to wait a little longer to understand its whole impact, which will for sure increase in importance in the next decades.

The terminology used for this process has not been completely determined yet. The most usual terms are 'conversion', because a word is converted (shifted) to a different part of speech; also 'zero-derivation' is used because the process is like deriving (transferring) a word into another morphological category with a zero-affix creating a semantic dependence of one word upon another.¹³ This would imply that this affix exists because it is grammatically meaningful although it cannot be seen. Other less frequently used terms are 'functional shift', 'functional change' or 'zero-marked derivative'¹⁴, denominations that express by themselves the way the process is considered to happen.

¹²Plag, I. "Word-formation in English", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2002, p.134,135

¹³ Hernández Bartolomé, Ana I. and Mendiluce Cabrera, G. "Grammatical Conversion in English: Some new trends in lexical evolution", Universidad de Valladolid

¹⁴ Cannon, G. "Functional Shift in English." *Linguistics*, 1985, p. 412

Conversion is extremely productive to increase the English lexicon because it provides an easy way to create new words from existing ones. Thus, the meaning is perfectly comprehensible and the speaker can rapidly fill a meaningful gap in his language or use fewer words.¹⁵ "Conversion is a totally free process and any lexeme can undergo conversion into any of the open form classes as the need arises."¹⁶ This means that any word form can be shifted to any word class, especially to open classes—nouns, verbs, etc.—and that there are not morphological restrictions. Up to date, there has only been found one restriction: derived nouns rarely undergo conversion (particularly not to verbs). This exception is easily understood: if there already exists one word in the language, the creation of a new term for this same concept will be blocked for the economy of language. For example, the noun 'denial'.

e.g. *This embrace included an emphatic rejection of denial or minimization of the Holocaust, will never shift into a verb because this word already derives from the verb 'deny'* e.g. *The Florida manual recount process is being used to eliminate any possibility of an orderly, rational, and final end to the election, and to deny the protections of the Constitution not only to the parties who brought the case, but to all Americans.*¹⁷

In that case, the conversion is blocked because 'to deny' and 'to denial' would mean exactly the same. However, there are some special cases in which this process seems to happen without blocking. This can be illustrated in the noun 'sign'

E.g. *Gore showed no sign of pain or remorse.*

Converted into the verb 'to sign' e.g. *'The Goreans quickly pointed out that there had already been a hand count in the Florida presidential race, and that Bush himself had signed a law calling for their use in Texas'* changed by derivation (suffixation) into the noun 'signal' e.g. *'A few days ago in Manhattan, Ms. Yrjola was in her apartment in the middle of a high-rise in the middle of everywhere when she could not even get a decent signal on her handset'* and converted into a new verb, 'to signal' e.g. *'Laughter seems to signal an attempt to ingratiate oneself: in India, notes Provine, men of lower castes giggle when addressing men of higher castes, but never the other way round.'*

It must be pointed out that the process of conversion has some semantic limitations: a converted word only assumes one of the range of meanings of the original word. For example, the noun 'paper' has various meanings, such as "newspaper" e.g. *'His wife was reading the paper, too nervous to deal with it.'*

¹⁵ Aitchison, J. "Words in the Mind—An Introduction to the Mental Lexicon", Basil Blackwell, Oxford, 1989, p.161

¹⁶ Bauer, L. "English Word Formation" Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1983, p.226

¹⁷ Hernández Bartolomé, Ana I. and Mendiluce Cabrera, G. "Grammatical Conversion in English: Some new trends in lexical evolution", Universidad de Valladolid

The aim of conversion varies with the user. Adults convey it to use fewer words, whereas children perform it in order to be understood, although they frequently produce ungrammatical utterances.¹⁸ Anyway, it always helps to make communication easier.

• Conversion from verb to noun

We shall first study the shift from verb to noun. It can be regarded from seven different points of view. These sub classifications are not well defined in many cases. The same pair of converted words can be placed into two different categories depending on the subjectivity of their meaning. Nouns coming from verbs can express state of mind or state of sensation, like in the nouns 'experience' e.g. *'The election had been "the most emotionally draining experience of my life.'* 'Fear' E.g. *'Yet one day they may long for a time when mothers shopped and left babies, without fear, in strollers on the sidewalk, and everyone had a right to a home, free education and medical care.'* The object of the verb from which the noun is derived can be observed in 'visit' (with the sense of that which visits), 'increase' (that which increases), 'call' and 'command'. In the fourth division the noun refers to the subject of the original verb. Examples of this kind are 'clone' (the living being that is cloned), 'contacts' or 'judge'. Other nouns show the instrument of the primitive verb, like in 'cover' (something to cover with) and 'start'. Finally, a place of the verb can also be nominalised, like in 'turn' (where to turn) or 'rise'.

• Conversion from noun to verb

Verbs converted from nouns have also many sub classifications. They can express the action of putting in or on the noun, such as in 'pocket(ed)' (to put into the pocket), 'film(ing)' (to put into a film) and 'practice'. These verbs can also have the meaning of "to provide with (the noun)" or "to give (the noun)", like 'name' (to give a name to somebody), 'shape' (to give shape to something) or 'fuel(s)'. The verbs belonging to the third division will express the action done with the noun as instrument. It can be exemplified with 'hammer' (to hit a nail by means of a hammer), 'yo-yo' (to play with a yo-yo) 'dot' or 'brake' (braking). Another group of verbs has the meaning of to act as the noun with respect to something, as exemplified in 'host(ed)' (to act as the host of a house). Other sub classification has the sense of making something into the original noun, like in 'schedule (d)' (41) (to arrange into a schedule) and 'rule' (42). The last group means to send by means of the noun, which is the case of 'ship (ped)' (43) or 'telephone (d)' (in an abstract sense).

• Conversion from adjective to verb

Adjectives can also go through the process of conversion, especially to verbs. De-adjectival verbs get the meaning of "to make (adjective)". It can be easily seen by means of examples like 'black(ed)' (to make black), 'open', 'slow(ing)' etc. In some cases, when these transitive verbs are used intransitively, a secondary conversion may happen,¹⁹ as it will be explained later on.

¹⁸ Aitchison, J. "Words in the Mind—An Introduction to the Mental Lexicon", Basil Blackwell, Oxford, 1989, p.161

¹⁹ Quirk, R. "A Comprehensive Grammar of the English Language", Longman, Essex, 1997, p. 1561, 1562

• Conversion from a closed category to any other category

Closed-class categories can also undergo conversion. Although their frequency is much less common, the process is not ungrammatical. All morphologic categories have examples of this kind.²⁰ Prepositions are probably the most productive ones. They can easily become adverbs, nouns and verbs. This is the case of 'up' e.g. '*Tiffany jumped up and down and hugged her girls and everyone else in sight*' and 'out'. Conversion to noun may as well occur in adverbs like in 'outside' and 'inside' e.g. '*This company had a credibility gap between the image that it cultivated with the African-American community on the outside and how African-Americans were treated on the inside,*' said the lawyer who negotiated a \$140 million cash settlement in a discrimination suit against Texaco in 1996'; conjunctions, as regarded in 'ifs' and 'buts' '*there's no ifs ands or buts about that,- said Carl*'; interjections and non-lexical items, like 'ho ho ho's' and 'ha haha'; affixes such as 'mini-' can appear as noun and proper noun etc. Conversion to verb is frequent in onomatopoeic expressions like 'buzz', 'beep' or 'woo(ing)'. Finally, phrase compounds can appear as adjectives, such as in 'borrow-the-mower', 'down-to-earth' or 'now-it-can-be-told'.

Conversion, in Albanian language, is the means of forming a new word as a result of switching into another part of speech because of the syntactical conditions in its use. Switching into another part of speech, the formed word this way changes its paradigm (it gains a new paradigm), or it loses it (when an open class word lapses into a closed class word).

There are two groups of words formed by conversion:

1. Closed classes words which distinguishes two subgroups:
 - a) Closed classes words that come from closed classes words, e.g. preposition from adverbs: *afer, anes, brenda, permes, prane, siper*etc.; conjunctions from adverbs: *ku, kur, nga* etc.; particles from adverbs: *vetem, plot, gati* etc. and from conjunctions: *sapo, posa, edhe*etc.
 - b) Closed classes words coming from open classes words, e.g. adverbs: *vjet, mot, sheshit, hapur, ndenjur, shkoqure*etc.; prepositions: *buze, rreth, mes, rreze*etc.; conjunctions: *dac, qofte*; particles: *le, desh*; interjections: *qyqja, korba, forca, o burra*, etc.
2. Open classes words. With conversion nouns are formed from adjectives and (tepanyjshem) adjectives from nouns. Turning into noun, adjective saves its basic lexical meaning of the quality and feature it expresses. E.g. *e verdha (e vezes), e bardha (e syrit), telashtat, iri*etc. Also nouns turn to adjectives. E.g. *kyc (problem kyc), kukull (qeverikukull), plak (burreplak), bullgar, ilir, freng, kelt*, etc.²¹

²⁰Cannon, G. "Functional Shift in English." *Linguistics*, 1985, p. 425, 426

²¹Jashari, A. and Kryeziu, B. "Gjuhe Amtare: (njohuri per gjuhen, fonetike, morfologji, sintakse)", Universiteti i Prishtines, Prishtine, 2011, p.42, 43

2.3 Adverbs derived from adjectives

Adverbs are words belonging to one of the major form classes in any of numerous languages, typically serving as a modifier of a verb.²² The vast majority of adverbs actually derive from another part of speech. Most of them derived from adjectives by adding an *-ly* suffix. Here are some examples:

Adjective	Adverb
<i>abrupt</i>	<i>abruptly</i>
<i>firm</i>	<i>firmly</i>
<i>honest</i>	<i>honestly</i>
<i>quick</i>	<i>quickly</i>
<i>sad</i>	<i>sadly</i>
<i>slow</i>	<i>slowly</i>
<i>soft</i>	<i>softly</i>

Even though there is a big number of adjectives that can end in *-ly*, here are some groups of adjectives that have no corresponding *-ly* adverb forms:

Nationality

<i>American</i>	<i>Americanly</i>
<i>Chinese</i>	<i>Chinesely</i>
<i>French</i>	<i>Frenchly</i>

Dimensions

<i>big</i>	<i>bigly</i>
<i>fat</i>	<i>fatly</i>
<i>tall</i>	<i>tally</i>

Age

<i>old</i>	<i>oldly</i>
<i>teenage</i>	<i>teenagely</i>
<i>young</i>	<i>youngly</i> ²³

2.4 Nouns derived from nouns

It doesn't mean that all derivation processes change word class. This 'gappiness' helps to confirm that these affixes are derivational rather than inflectional even though they do not change

²² Merriam-Webster's 11th Collegiate Dictionary

²³ <http://esl.enkouyu.com/grammar/523-adverbs-derived-from-adjectives-by-adding-an-ly-suffix.html>

the word class. These examples GLASWEGIAN, LOGICIAN and HISTORIAN illustrate at least superficially, the possibility that the base for a derivational process may be bound rather than free.

2.5 Nouns derived from members of other word classes

Nouns derived from adjectives and from verbs are extremely numerous, and it should be easy for you to think of many other examples on the lines of those given here. Here are some suffixes used to derive nouns from adjectives:

-ity, e.g. purity, equality, sensitivity
-ness, e.g. goodness, tallness, sensitiveness
*-ism, e.g. radicalism, conservatism*²⁴

2.6 Adjectives derived from adjectives

In this category, prefixes predominate. The only suffix of note is *-ish*, meaning ‘somewhat X’, as in *greenish, smallish, remotish* ‘rather remote’. By contrast, the prefixes *un-* meaning ‘not’ is extremely widespread: for example, *unhappy, unsure, unreliable, undiscovered*. Because it is so common, most dictionaries do not attempt to list all *un-* adjectives. This does not mean, however, that *un-* can be prefixed to all adjectives quite freely, we do not find, for example, *ungood* with the meaning ‘bad’.

Another negative prefix is *in-*, with allomorphs indicated by the variant spellings *il-*, *ir-*, and *im-* as *inintangible, illegal, irresponsible, and impossible*. It is more restricted than *un-*, largely for historical reasons. For the present it is worth noting the existence of pairs of more or less synonymous adjectives, one of which is negated with *un-* and the other with *in-* or one of its allomorphs:

<i>Eatable / uneatable</i>	<i>edible / inedible</i>
<i>Readable / unreadable</i>	<i>legible / illegible</i>
<i>Lawful / unlawful</i>	<i>legal / illegal</i>
<i>Touchable / untouchable</i>	<i>tangible / intangible</i>

Such examples confirm that the use of *in-* is lexically restricted. As the negative counterpart of *edible, inedible* sounds possible, especially if the speaker has limited education and has not encountered, or has momentarily forgotten, the form *inedible*. However, *ineatable* as the counterpart of *eatable* is not a form that any English speaker would spontaneously use.

²⁴Carstairs-McCarthy, A. “An Introduction to English Morphology: Words and their Structure” E.U. Press Ltd 2002 Edinburgh, p.

2.7 Adjectives derived from members of other word class

Some of the processes that derived adjectives from verbs straddle the divide between derivation and inflection in a way that we have not yet encountered. We have learned about the suffixes -ed, -en, -ing, and vowel change, in passive and progressive participle form of verb. However, such form can also be adjectives:

1. a. *a not very interesting book*
- b. *the party –goers sounded very drunk.*
- c. *the car seemed more damaged than the lamp-post.*

The modifier *very* and the comparative construction (more ...than) show that *interesting*, *drunk* and *damaged* are adjectives here, not forms of the verb lexemes *interest*, *drink*, and *damaged*.

Further suffixes that commonly form adjectives from verbs, with their basic meaning are:

2. –able: *breakable, readable, reliable, and watchable*
3. –ent,-ant: *repellent, expectant, conversant*
4. –ive: *repulsive, explosive, and speculative*

Expectations derived from these basic meaning can, as usual in derivation; for example, *conversant* does not mean ‘tending to converse’. We have already encountered –able, where the variant, or allomorph, -ible is also illustrated. Suffixes that form adjectives from noun are more numerous. Here are some:

5. –ful: *joyful, hopeful, helpful, and meaningful*
6. –less: *joyless, hopeless, helpless, and meaningless*
7. –al: *original, normal, personal, and national*
8. –ish: *boyish, loutish, waspish, and selfish*

As will be seen, adjectives in –ful and –less tend to come in pairs, although the correspondence is not exact: we have *slothful* but not *slothless*, and *penniless* but not *pannifull*. This confirms again that even when the meaning of a potential word may be easily guessable (a *slothless* person would be hard working, and a *pannifull* person would be well off), the existence of the word is not guaranteed.²⁵

2.8 Verbs derived from verbs

Most of the verbs derived from verbs take the prefixes re-, un-, and dis-. E.g.

paint – repaint

tie – untie

²⁵Ibrahimi, S. and Iseni, A. “Modern English Grammar” Tetova, 2008, p.105, 106

compose – decompose
entangle – disentangle

Also worth mentioning here is the relationship between the verbs in the left and right columns in:

Intransitive - Transitive
Lie (past lay) - lay (past laid)
Rise (past rose) - raise (past raised)
Fall (past fell) - fell (past felled)
Sit (past sat) - set (past set)

Transitive verbs (or verbs used transitively) are ones with an ‘object’ noun phrase, usually indicating the thing or person that is the goal of the action of the verb, as *the book* is the object of *laid* in the example below:

Jill laid the book on the table.

And intransitive verbs, such as *lay* in the example below, lack such an object.

*The book lay on the table.*²⁶

2.9 Verbs derived from members of other word classes

Some affixes that contribute in the derivation of verbs from nouns and adjectives are:

de-, debug, defrost, delonse
-ise, organize, patronize, terrorise
*-(i)fy, beautify, gentrify, petrify*²⁷

Also some verbs are derived from nouns by replacing the last voiceless consonant of the noun with a voiced consonant.

Nouns	Verbs
<i>bath</i>	<i>bathe</i>
<i>breath</i>	<i>breathe</i>
<i>house (s)</i>	<i>house (z)</i>
<i>wreath</i>	<i>wreathe</i>

²⁶ Carstairs-McCarthy, A. “An Introduction to English Morphology: Words and Their Structure”, Edinburgh University Press, Edinburgh, 2002, p. 54

²⁷ Carstairs-McCarthy, A. “An Introduction to English Morphology: Words and Their Structure”, Edinburgh University Press, Edinburgh, 2002, p. 55

It is obvious that suffixes are more important than prefixes in English derivational morphology.

Conclusion

Most new words are not as new as we tend to think. They can undergo many different word formation processes to create a new lexicon. Some of these processes are more lexicalized, such as derivation or compounding some of them are less lexicalized as: conversion, blending clipping, etc. the derivation process most of the time involves changes in form, like prefixing and suffixing. In English it is allowed to change words part of speech without changing the form. Both languages, English and Albanian, are very rich with derived words. Also they both have four kinds of derivations: prefix derivations, suffix derivations, affixation in English but prefix-suffix in Albanian and conversion in English but non affix derivations in Albanian.

When it comes to lexemes, English and Albanian linguists have treated different things. English linguists have dealt with the shapes of lexemes that appear in dictionaries which spell out word forms. While the Albanian linguists consider in the interest of word formation distinguishing the lexemes; a lexeme is the part of word that remains after we remove the endings and suffixes, A word-forming lexeme is a lexeme by which is formed a (jo e parme) lexeme and a morphological lexeme is the part of word that remains after we remove only the ending.

Words have various functions in syntax. Each language has its own set of syntactic categories, and definitions of them, but there are some big similarities between the languages across the Europe. These similarities exist between English and Albanian word classes. Context and the use make it easier to recognize the word class. Another element that helps identifying the word class are the suffixes. The word classes in English are: open word classes (nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs) and closed word classes (pronouns, determiners, particles, prepositions). In Albanian open word classes are: noun, pronoun, adjective, verb and numeral and closed word classes: adverb, preposition, conjunction, particles and interjection. There is a difference between the two languages because Albanian includes adverbs in closed word classes, while in English it is a part of open word classes. Also pronoun in Albanian goes with open classes and conjunction and interjection are not listed in neither word class.

Conversion is extremely productive to increase the English lexicon because it provides an easy way to create new words from existing ones. English linguists have put conversion in the word formation group, but they are still considering if it should be a branch of derivation or a separate process. Even though it is very productive, it is supposed that it will be more productive in the future. Conversion in Albanian distinguishes two groups of words: closed classes words which distinguishes two subgroups (closed classes words that come from closed classes words) and closed classes words coming from open classes words. While in English conversion deals with the shaping of word in dictionaries, the Albanian language gives the classification written above.

I have also tried to elaborate shortly about adverbs derived from adjectives, nouns derived from nouns, nouns derived from other word classes, adjectives derived from adjectives, adjectives derived from members of other word classes, verbs derived from verbs and verbs derived from members of other word classes, but there was not enough information. In the other side after researching in different books and consulting a linguist, I came to an ending that they do not exist in Albanian language.

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